

VALIDATION OF OPENSTUDIO SIMULATION TOOL FOR PASSIVE INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL COMFORT IN MIDRISE OFFICE BUILDINGS IN TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Studies have revealed that, one of the frequent questions that is usually raised by researchers who use computer simulation is, “how can they be sure that the software is of a sufficient standard to justify its use?” Consequently, this called for the validation of simulation tool at the beginning of every research that involves the use of simulation. The study is therefore aimed at validating Openstudio simulation tool and was achieved by taking physical measurements in some offices of Ahmadu Bello University Senate building and Nagwamatse house Kaduna. Google sketch-up 2017 and openstudio simulation tools were used to model the corresponding virtual buildings. The data generated was then analysed using statistical tools such as bar charts and tables. The results showed a strong positive correlation with the average measure Correlation Coefficient of 0.97 at 95% confidence level and average p-value of .015.

Keywords: Climate, Indoor Environmental Comfort, Midrise building, Open-studio, Validation.

INTRODUCTION

A midrise office building is any office building with 4 to 12 floors, as classified by Alcox (2017) and Freedman, (2009). Passive Indoor Environmental Comfort (PIEC) in this research is defined as the condition of architectural space (office) where Optimum thermal, and visual comfort are maintained by natural means. Evaluating PIEC could be done using Analytical testing, Experimentation, or Computer simulation. Analytical method uses heat balance concept (Xiao, Wang, Zhang, 2009) which has been rejected by the study, while the result from the Experimental are vulnerable to errors and takes time (de Dear & Auliciems, 1988), Whereas Simulation is efficient in solving both simple and complex building conditions (Gilber, 2013).

The history of computer simulation dates back to World War II when two mathematicians Jon Von Neumann and Stanislaw Ulam were faced with the puzzling problem of behavior of neutrons. Hit and trial experimentation were too costly and the problem was too complicated

for analysis (Robeson, & Howe 1994). OpenStudio is a collection of software tools which was designed to support the entire building energy modeling using EnergyPlus and Radiance. It is a plugin for Sketch-Up and was first released in April 2008 by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, a part of the U.S. Department of Energy (Garthwaite, 2009). One of the leading methods of conducting research in Architecture in today's world is Computer simulation. It was defined by Eric (2019) as the process of mathematical modelling, performed on a computer, which is designed to predict the behavior of the real world.

One of the frequent questions that is usually raised by the users of computer simulation tools as observed by Parkin and Barker (2007) is, "how can they be sure that the software is of a sufficient standard to justify its use?" This therefore called for the validation of simulation software at the beginning of every research that involves the use of simulation. Validation of the simulations is required to ascertain that the software chosen and user are able to adequately model the buildings and imitates the reality. Jacobson and Jacobson (2015) defined validation as the confirmation and provision of objective evidence that the particular requirements for a specific intended use are fulfilled. It is simply the ability of the instrument to measure what is intended to measure. Sargent, (2011) has observed that, since the simulation models are approximate imitations of real world systems and they never exactly imitate the real world system, there is need to validate both the software and the model developed by the software.

Openstudio simulation tool has been validated by a number of researchers such as Guglielmetti, Pless and Torcellini, (2010); An, and Mason, (2010); Guglielmetti, and Ball, (2016); and Kamel, and Memari, (2018). However none of these studies was done in composite tropical climate in the whole of Africa. This study is therefore aimed at validating Openstudio Simulation in temperate-dry climate of Nigeria. It was done by measuring the task illuminance, relative humidity, and operative temperature in the 13 selected offices of Ahmadu Bello University senate building in Zaria and Nagwamatse house in Kaduna; and also measured the task illuminance, relative humidity and operative temperature in the 13 modelled offices of ABU senate building Zaria and Nagwamatse buildings in Zaria and kaduna using OpenStudio simulation tool; and lastly compared and contrast the physical and simulated values between the real and virtual buildings using statistical tools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review has revealed that, there is no single test that would 100% ascertain the validity of the software, but Forrester, and Senge (1980) observed that, the level of confidence in the simulation software can increase gradually as it passes more tests. Judkoff, Wortman, O'Doherty, and Burch (2008b) proposed three categories of validation in an attempt to minimize the uncertainty of the extrapolations: Comparative tests, which compare against other software; Analytical tests, which compare against mathematical solution; and Empirical tests, which compare against experimental data. Each approach focuses on different aspects of the validation problem. They believed that, by integrating these approaches in the overall validation process, the advantages of each are enhanced and the disadvantages minimized.

Sargent (2011) has identified 4 four methods of validating simulation software and model. The first one is the decision by the model development team that is to make the resolution as to whether a simulation model is valid. This method is very subjective and is made based on the results of the various tests and evaluations conducted as part of the model development process. The next one is to have the user(s) of the model heavily involved with the model development team in deciding the validity of the simulation software and the model. In this approach the focus of determining the validity of the simulation software and the model produced moves

from the model developers to the model users. Another approach is known as independent verification and validation (IV&V). It uses a third party to decide whether the simulation model as well as the software are valid. The last approach is to use a scoring model. Scores are determined subjectively when conducting various aspects of the validation process and then combined to determine category scores and an overall score for the simulation model. This approach is seldom used in practice.

Crawley, (2001) categorized validation software into five groups: Analytical tests which compare against mathematical solution; Comparative tests which compare against other software; Sensitivity tests which compare small inputs changes versus a base line run; Range tests which exercise the program over wide range of input values; and Empirical tests which compare against experimental data. Empirical validation was selected for this study due to its relative advantage over others such as accuracy as against Analytical test which has accuracy problem as observed by Cawley (2001), and has no issue in energy and humidity ratio as in Comparative test as noted by Ali, Khan, Iqbal, Butt, Khan, and Umer, (2015).

Climate classifications can be grouped into three essential types, which are: empiric; genetic; and applied climate classifications (Guglielmetti, Macumber, and Long, 2011). This depends on type of the data used for classification. Köppen’s and Miller’s climate classifications were based on vegetations while Thornthwaites’ was based on agriculture, and Atkinson’s was based on thermal comfort. Koenigsberger, Ingersoll, Mayhew, and Szokolay, (2013) have observed that, most climates categorizations that are based on human comfort have their origin from Atkinson (1953)’s classification, such as Koenigsberger’s, Komolafe and Agwal’s classifications, Olufowobi’s, Szokolay’s, Ogunsote and Prucnal-Ogunsote’s climate classifications and Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020) classification. The research has adopted the Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020) climate classification as it is the only one that factored temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature and wind velocity as its determinants. Therefore its classification is based on Comfort and Bioclimatic Approach, as shown in figure 2.1.

Fig. 2.1. Classification of the Nigerian climate Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020).

METHODOLOGY

Empirical method of validation was used due to its approximate truth standard within accuracy of measurements as observed by Judkoff, Wortman, O’Doherty, and Burch (2008b) and it is the one recommended by the IEA (1995). The assessments of PIEC parameters in the existing and prototype virtual offices in temperate-dry climatic of Nigeria with respect to task illuminance measurements, operative temperature, and relative humidity was conducted. The relationship between the measured and simulated values was evaluated using statistical tests for the correlation and levels of significance. Detailed procedures and tools for this stage are listed in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Detailed Validation Study Procedures. Source: Author, 2018

Physical Measurement

For the physical measurements, Senate building of Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria; and the New Nigeria News Paper office building (Nagwamatse house) Kaduna were used which were selected based on a convenience non-probability sampling technique. The criteria used in the selection was based on the difference in their Orientations, and building layout. Other selection criteria include: number of storeys (mid-rise buildings); access to buildings; and HVAC system. Access to the building here means, the readiness of office buildings’ management to allow such kind of activity to take place in their buildings due to privacy and security situation of the country. On the issue of HVAC system, most of the midrise office buildings rely on both mechanical and natural means provision of their IEC, and this research is limited to passive means. For these reasons, all artificial light, mechanical ceiling fan and AC, were put-off throughout the period of measurements. Moreover, all windows, blinds and curtains were also opened for natural ventilation and all doors were to be closed within the period of measurements.

Thirteen (13) number of offices in ABU Senate building and Nagwamatse house were used for physical measurements as shown in Figure 3.1; Plates I; and II.

Table 3.1 Study offices in ABU Senate building and Nagwamatse office building

S/No.	Building Name	Location	Building Form	Building Orientation	Floor level	Office Tag.	Ownership	
							Public	Private
1	ABU Senate building	Samaru, Zaria	Single-banked	315 ⁰	1st	Academic Office	1	0
					3 rd	Computer Room	1	0
					4 th	Filing Room	1	0
					5 th	Record Office	1	0
					6 th	Secretary to Human Resources	1	0
					8 th	Office/Store	1	0
2	New Nigeria News Paper office Building	Nagwamuts e House, Kaduna, metropolis	Double-banked	90 ⁰	1 st	MD's office	0	1
					2 nd	Estate Surveyors	0	1
					3 rd	MD AA Usman & CO	0	1
					4 th	Mother Care, Gen. Office	0	1
					5 th	Drawing Office	0	1
					6 th	KD Consults	0	1
					8 th	Accounting Office	0	1

Plate I. Offices of Senate Building, ABU Zaria
Source: Author and Google Maps (2018)

Plate II. Offices of NNNP Building, Nagwamatse House, Kaduna
Source: Author and Google Maps (2018)

The following documents were used for both physical and simulation measurements: Daylighting Monitoring Protocols & Procedures for Buildings, 1997; Monitoring Procedures for Assessment of Daylighting Performance of Buildings, 2001 (both published by the International Energy Agency IEA); 2012 International Energy Conservation Code, USA; National Research Council Canada, 1997; ASHRAE standards; and Indoor Air Quality Handbook, 2003.

Table 3.2 summarises the methods and procedures which were used during physical measurements.

Table 3.2. Calibration details during the research measurements

<i>S/NO</i>	<i>IEQ Parameter</i>	<i>Measurement variables</i>	<i>Sample Position</i>	<i>Height above Floor</i>	<i>Measurement Period</i>	<i>Acceptable Benchmark for Offices</i>	<i>Instruments</i>
1	Thermal Comfort	Temperature	At the center of the office Or Work station Or 1.0m from the center of the largest window	100mm, 600mm and 1100mm (ASHRAE 55 (2010))	Every 5mints for 2hrs (ASHRAE 55 (2010))	24.3-29.3 °C (ASHRAE 55 (2017))	Thermometer; Kestrel meter 5000.
		Relative Humidity	1.0m from the center of the largest window (ASHRAE 55 (2010))	600mm (ASHRAE 55 (2010))	Every 5mints for 2hrs (ASHRAE 55 (2010))	30-65% (ASHRAE 55 (2010), WHO, ISO7730)	Hygrometer, Kestrel meter 5000.
2	Daylight	Task illuminance level (lux)	test points on the sidewalls should be 1 meter away from the walls (National Research Council Canada, 1997)	At the height of work plane or 750mm to 800mm (NREL, 2011)	5mints for 2hrs (ASHRAE 90.1 ,2010); 4mints for 2hrs (Atif, Love, & Littlefair, 1997)	500Lux ISO 8995-1, (2002) & IESNA Lighting Handbook	illuminance meter,

Source: Author, 2018

Simulation of PIEC of Office buildings

Based on the afore-mentioned documents the following steps were followed:

- i. ABU senate building and Nagwamatse house were modelled in google sketch-up, including all properties of materials and ground reflectance;

Figure 1. Simulated PIEC of the Offices in Nagwamatse ABU Senate building, Zaria.

Figure 2. Simulated PIEC of the Offices building, Kaduna.

Source: Author, 2018

- ii. In order to simulate PIEC components, such as daylight and thermal comfort, EnergyPlus weather (EPW) was used as the type of weather file;
- iii. Sketch-up plugging called Open-studio was used to set weather files of Zaria, and Kaduna, from weather Analytic;
- iv. Radiance measure for daylight and open-studio for thermal comfort were used;
- v. Space types, thermal zones, and construction materials were selected;
- vi. Zone Air Relative humidity and Zone Operative Temperature, were selected from output variables;
- vii. from January to December of 2018 was selected from Simulation settings;
- viii. Simulation button was pressed for the final analysis.

For the purpose of Hypothesis testing a Microsoft Excel Data Analysis Pack was used to analyse data from the Radiance and open-studio simulation tools.

Based on the IEA, NREL and ASHRAE documents referred earlier, there were these phases of monitoring as indicated on table 3.5a, b, c, and d.

Table 3.5a Decision/Preparatory/Monitoring Document on Offices

<i>I.</i>		<i>General information on test rooms</i>
<i>Location</i>		Nagwamatse House, Kaduna
<i>Latitude and longitude</i>		10°31'55.94"N / 7°25'42.97"E, 10°31'55.42"N / 7°25'43.01"E, 10°31'55.421"N / 7°25'43.19"E, 10°31'54.46"N / 7°25'43.31"E, 10°31'54.47"N / 7°25'43.83"E, 10°31'55.91"N / 7°25'43.64"E
<i>Elevation (m)</i>		628/ 628/ 628/ 627/ 627/ 628 respectively

<i>Orientation of whole building. (N=0°, E=90°, S=180°, W=270°)</i>	90°						
<i>Office name</i>	MD's office	Estate surveyor	AA Usman & CO	Mother care Office	Drawing office	KD Consult	Accounting Office
<i>Floor level</i>	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	8 th
<i>Electric appliances</i>	Off						
<i>Time and date of measurements</i>	8:28am 11/05/18	9.05am 11/05/18	9.20am 11/05/18	9.44am 11/05/18	10.22am 11/05/18	10.50am 11/05/18	11.36am 11/05/18
<i>Orientation of test rooms (N=0°, E=90°, S=180°, W=270°)</i>	90°		270°		90°		270°
<i>Internal length, width & height</i>	5m, 5m and 3.18m	5m, 3.5m and 3.18m	5m, 3.5m and 2.66m	7.2m, 5m and 3.33m	5m, 5m and 3.18m	5m, 5m and 3.5m	5m, 3 m and 3.45m
<i>Window to wall ratio</i>	10%	11.8%	10.6%	11.8%	5%	10.8%	7.2%
<i>Were the rooms occupied during measurements</i>	No						
<i>Activity period</i>	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm
<i>Occupant's activities</i>	Mostly paper based tasks						

Table 3.5b Decision/Preparatory/Monitoring Document on Offices

2.	General information on test rooms						
<i>Location</i>	ABU Senate Building, Zaria						
<i>Latitude and longitude</i>	11°09'03.11''N / 7°39'20.32''E, 11°09'01.98''N / 7°39'21.21''E, 11°09'02.95''N / 7°39'22.33''E, 11°09'03.96''N / 7°39'21.41''E						
<i>Elevation (m)</i>	675/ 674/ 675/ 676 respectively.						
<i>Orientation of whole building. (N=0°, E=90°, S=180°, W=270°)</i>	315°						
<i>Office name</i>	Academic office	Computer Room	Head Bursary Filing Room	Record Office	Secretary to Human Resource	Office/ Store	
<i>Floor level</i>	1 st	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	8 th	
<i>Electric appliances</i>	Off	Off	Off	Off	Off	Off	
<i>Time and date of measurements</i>	12.40PM 14/05/18	3.00PM 14/05/18	1.00PM 14/05/18	1.20PM 14/05/18	1.45PM 14/05/18	2.30PM 14/05/18	
<i>Orientation of test rooms (N=0°, E=90°, S=180°, W=270°)</i>	315°		315°/135°		225°		45°
<i>Internal length, width & height</i>	8m, 10m and 3.57m	6.5m, 6.5m and 3.05m	6.5m, 3.5m and 3.57m	6.5m, 6.5m and 3.5m	5m, 5m and 3.46m	6.5m, 4m and 2.8m	
<i>Window to wall ratio</i>	12.7%	27.5%	6.8%	9%	2.4%	10.7%	
<i>Were the rooms occupied during measurements</i>	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

<i>Activity period</i>	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm	5 days a week, from 8:00am to 5:00pm
<i>Occupant's activities</i>	Mostly paper based tasks					

Table 3.5c Decision/Preparatory/Monitoring Document on Offices

3. General Material Properties						
	Material	Conductivity (W/mK)	Specific heat (J/KgK)	Thermal Absorptance	Solar Absorptance	Visible Absorptance
<i>Exterior wall surfaces</i>	Plaster	0.58	1090	0.9	0.7	0.7
	Sand create block	1.23	976	0.9	0.7	0.7
<i>Floor</i>	Concrete	1.73	837	0.9	0.65	0.65
	Acoustic tile	0.06	590	0.9	0.3	0.3
<i>Ceiling</i>	Concrete Decking	0.53	840	0.9	0.5	0.5
	Gypsum board	0.16	1090	0.9	0.4	0.4
<i>Roofing material</i>	Metal	45	418	0.9	0.6	0.6
	Roof Insulation	0.16	1460	0.9	0.7	0.7

Table 3.5d Decision/Preparatory/Monitoring Document on Offices.

4.			
<i>Variable to be measured</i>	illuminance	Temperature	Relative humidity
<i>Measuring Tool</i>	Martindale Illuminance Meter LM 9	Kestrel meter 5000	Kestrel meter 5000
<i>Number of sensors</i>	9	3	3
<i>Height above floor</i>	800mm	100mm, 600mm and 1100mm	600mm
<i>Variable to be measured</i>	Reflectance Measurements for walls, ceiling & floor	Operative temperature	Air humidity

Source: Author (2018)

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

The measured and simulated PIEC parameters were analysed using Anova statistical test to find the correlation and significance of the relationships. Moreover, mean bias error and root mean square were also used to ascertain the relationships.

Simulation and Measured Results

The measured and simulated data are listed in Tables 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9, 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12.

Table 4.1 Simulated illuminances of the Academic Office (1st floor) in ABU Senate building Zaria,

<i>Sensor Points</i>	<i>Measured (Lux)</i>	<i>Simulated (Lux)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
2	702	577	125	125	15,625
3	333	284	49	49	2,401
4	512	472	40	40	1,600
5	301	338	-37	37	1,369
6	514	573	59	59	3,481
7	536	498	38	38	1,444
8	331	475	-144	144	20,736
9	327	424	-97	97	9,409
9	271	267	4	4	16
<i>AVERAGE</i>	425.2		4.11		6,2312.2

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.2 Simulated illuminances of the Estate Surveyors' Office (2nd floor) in Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor Points</i>	<i>Measured (Lux)</i>	<i>Simulated (Lux)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	655	611	44	44	1936
2	217	220	17	17	289
3	1290	900	-390	390	152100
4	577	540	37	37	1369
5	270	250	20	20	400
6	408	450	-42	42	1764
7	144	130	14	14	196
8	536	498	38	38	1,444
9	917	850	67	67	4,489
<i>AVERAGE</i>	557.11		-195		18,220.78

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.3 Simulated illuminances of the Mother Care General Office (5th floor) in Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor Points</i>	<i>Measured (Lux)</i>	<i>Simulated (Lux)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	1077	1005	72	72	5,184
2	1000	1014	14	14	196
3	999	900	99	99	9801
4	514	525	-11	11	121
5	577	540	37	37	1,369
6	483	503	-20	20	400
7	254	230	24	24	576
8	396	380	16	16	256
9	381	368	13	13	169
<i>AVERAGE</i>	631.22		27.11		2,008

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.4 Simulated illuminances of the Store (8th floor) in ABU Senate building Zaria,

<i>Sensor Points</i>	<i>Measured (Lux)</i>	<i>Simulated (Lux)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	430	400	30	30	900
2	177	220	-43	43	1849
3	440	500	-60	60	3600
4	131	180	-49	49	2401
5	144	200	-56	56	3136
6	370	350	20	20	400
<i>AVERAGE</i>	282		-26.3333		2,047.667

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.5 Simulated Operative temperature of the Director's Office (1st floor) at Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (°C)</i>	<i>Simulated (°C)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	27.8	25.4	2.4	2.4	5.76
2	27	24.8	2.2	2.2	4.84
3	27.8	25.4	2.4	2.4	5.76
<i>AVERAGE</i>	27.53		2.33		5.45

Source: Author, 2018

Table 4.6 Simulated Operative temperature of the Computer Room (3rd floor) in ABU Senate building Zaria.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (°C)</i>	<i>Simulated (°C)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	31.4	28	3.4	3.4	11.56
2	30.4	25	5.4	5.4	29.16
3	31.1	27	4.1	4.1	16.81
<i>AVERAGE</i>	30.97		4.3		19.18

Source: Author, 2018

Table 4.7 Simulated Operative temperature of the Secretary to Human Resource office (6th floor) in ABU Senate building Zaria.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (°C)</i>	<i>Simulated (°C)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	24	25	-1	1	1
2	31.1	26.4	4.7	4.7	22.09
3	29.8	26.1	3.7	3.7	13.69
<i>AVERAGE</i>	28.3		2.27		12.26

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.8 Simulated Operative temperature of the *Accounting Office* (8th floor) at Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (°C)</i>	<i>Simulated (°C)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	27	25.7	1.3	1.3	1.69
2	26.9	25.7	1.2	1.2	1.44
3	24	24.8	-0.8	0.8	0.64
<i>AVERAGE</i>	25.97		0.57		1.26

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.9 Simulated Relative humidity of the *Director's Office* (1st floor) at Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (%)</i>	<i>Simulated (%)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	42	37.8	4.2	4.2	17.64
2	47	39	8	8	64
3	41	37.6	3.4	3.4	11.56
<i>AVERAGE</i>	43.3		5.2		31.07

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.10 Simulated Relative humidity of the *Computer Room* (3rd floor) at ABU Senate building Zaria.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (%)</i>	<i>Simulated (%)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	51.8	48.4	3.4	3.4	11.56
2	46	41.7	4.3	4.3	18.49
3	53	49.6	3.4	3.4	11.56
<i>AVERAGE</i>	50.27		3.7		13.87

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.11 Simulated Relative humidity of the *Secretary to Human Resource Office* (6th floor) at ABU Senate building Zaria.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (%)</i>	<i>Simulated (%)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	72.8	66	6.8	6.8	46.24
2	55.8	45	10.8	10.8	116.64
3	57	48.4	8.6	8.6	73.96
<i>AVERAGE</i>	61.87		8.73		78.95

Source: Author (2018)

Table 4.12 Simulated Relative humidity of the *Accounting Office* (8th floor) at Nagwamatse House, Kaduna.

<i>Sensor points</i>	<i>Measured (%)</i>	<i>Simulated (%)</i>	<i>Error (Mea-Sim)</i>	<i>Absolute Error</i>	<i>Error² (Mea-Sim)²</i>
1	41	37.2	3.8	3.8	14.44
2	41	37.5	3.5	3.5	12.25
3	50	43	7	7	49
<i>AVERAGE</i>	44		4.68		25.23

Source: Author, 2018

Tests of Relationships and Significance

To reveal how weak or strong the relationship between the two variables is, the ANOVA test was used to measure the degree and the significance of relationship as summaries in table 4.1. One can see the high degree of positive linear correlation between the measured and the simulated IEC parameters.

Table 4.1. Correlation Table between measured and simulated data of offices in ABU Senate building Zaria and Nagwamatse House Kaduna

Office Building	Tagged	Floor levels	r-value	p-value	Variable
ABU Senate building, Zaria	Academic Office	1 st	0.822	.0018	Illuminance
	Store	8 th	0.965	.0018	Illuminance
	Secretary Human Resource	6 th	0.99	.0204	Operative temperature
	Computer Room	3 rd	0.99	.0235	Operative temperature
	Secretary Human Resource	6 th	0.99	.0560	Relative humidity
	Computer Room	3 rd	0.99	.0125	Relative humidity
Nagwamatse house, Kaduna	Estate Surveyors	2 nd	0.97	.0000	Illuminance
	Mother-Care General Office	3 rd	0.99	.0000	Illuminance
	Director's Office	1 st	1	.0000	Operative temperature
	Accounting Office	8 th	0.99	.0187	Operative temperature
	Director's Office	1 st	0.99	.0125	Relative Humidity
	Accounting Office	8 th	0.99	.292	Relative humidity

Source: Author, (2018)

The degree of accuracy of correlation of each of the models was evaluated by means of two widely used statistical methods for simulation research: the mean bias error percentage (MBE); and the root mean square error percentage (RMSE) (Efim & Kudish, 2009, Katiyar et al., 2010, as cited in Salisu, 2013) as indicated on table 4.2

Table 4.2 Mean Bias Error (MBE) and Root Mean Square Error Percentage Values.

	Building	Office tag.	Floor	Size	N	$\sum(X_{mea-sim})$	$X_{mea(av)}$	$\sum(X_{mea-sim})^2$	% MBE	%RMSE
Illuminance	ABU Senate	Store	8 th floor	3.5m x 6.6m	6	-26.3333	282	2047.667	-9.34	16
		Academic Office	1 st floor	8m x 10m	9	37	425.2	56,801	9.67	18.56
	NNNP	Estate Surveyor	2 nd floor	7.5m x 5m	9	-195	557.11	163,987	-3.89	24.23
		Mother Care Gen. Office.	5 th floor	7.5m x 5m	9	244	631.22	18,072	4.3	7.1
Operative Temp.	ABU Senate	Secretary to Human Resource.	6 th floor	4.5m x 4.6m	3	6.81	28.3	36.78	8.02	12.37
		Computer Room	3 rd floor	6.6m x 6.5m	3	12.9	30.97	57.54	13.88	14.17
	NNNP	Director's Office	1 st floor	5m x 5m	3	7	27.53	16.35	8.48	8.49

Relative humidity	Accounting Office (MD)	8 th floor	5m x 5m	3	1.71	25.97	3.78	2.19	4.32	
	ABU Senate	Secretary to Human Resource.	6 th floor	4.5m x 4.6m	3	26.19	61.87	236.85	14.11	14.36
		Computer Room	3 rd floor	6.6m x 6.5m	3	11.1	50.27	41.61	7.36	7.41
	NNNP	Director's Office	1 st floor	5m x 5m	3	15.6	43.3	93.2	12	12.87
		Accounting Office (MD)	8 th floor	5m x 5m	3	14.04	44	75.69	10.64	11.42

Source: field work, 2018

For simulation data to be acceptable as reliable, the values of mean bias error (MBE) have to fall within a range of -15% to 15%, while for RMSE, the values have to be less than 35% (Reinhart, 2009, as cited in Salisu, 2013).

The MBE percentage is expressed as:

$$\% \text{ MBE} = \frac{100}{X_{\text{mean av}}} \sum \frac{(X_{\text{mea}} - X_{\text{sim}})}{N} \text{-----}4.1$$

RMSE percentage is expressed as:

$$\% \text{ RMSE} = \frac{100}{X_{\text{mean av}}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum (X_{\text{mea}} - X_{\text{sim}})^2} \text{-----}4.2$$

Where X_{mea} is the measured value of PIEC parameter, X_{sim} is the simulated value of IEC parameter, and $X_{\text{mea(av)}}$ is the average value of N measured of IEC parameter values. The values of both MBE and RMSE are low, indicating a fairly good agreement with the limits for reliability as shown on table 4.2.

The validity of an instrument is the ability of that instrument to measure what is intended to measure. Whereas, Reliability is defined as the consistency of the measuring instrument. It is important to note that, a measure can be reliable without being Valid, but cannot be valid without being reliable.

The results has satisfied all the three (3) major divisions of validity, which are: Content validity; Criterion related validity; and Construct validity. In the Content validity, the instrument was able to cover a range of constructs of IEC which are: relative humidity; operative temperature; and Illuminances. The difference between the measured and the simulated data are within the normal limit as recommended by Reinhart, (2009) (as cited in Salisu, 2013); and Efim & Kudish, (2009) (as cited in Salisu, 2013) as shown on table 4.2. It has also shows that the error is within acceptable levels. The errors may be due to the properties of some building materials which have started changing due to aging and lack of maintenance, especially in Nagwamatse house Kaduna. From the results, it can be deduced that, since the instrument was able to measure the past and the current performances, it can equally predict future performance and therefore satisfies Criterion validity. Criterion validity is when the results from the instrument accurately predicts some kind of external variance. It is of two types: predictive validity and

Concurrent validity. The instrument was also able to differentiate readings from different floor levels, building layouts and orientations. That means it has satisfied the Construct Validity test.

On the other hand, to measure the Reliability of the instrument, the Test and Retest method was used when measurements and simulations were done in the two (2) buildings. The results from the first time were compared to results from the second time and the third time in order to determine how well the instrument consistently gets the same results. In all the measurements the consistency was observed before it was recorded. The Equivalence reliability was also achieved whereby three observers had to agree on every measurements before it was recorded during the measurements/ simulations exercise.

CONCLUSION

The validation study was conducted in order to test the validity and reliability of data collection instruments and the analytical tools prior to the main study of PIEC in mid-rise office buildings in the temperate-dry climate of Nigeria. The Content, Criterion related and Construct validity were achieved through a thorough evaluation of the instruments. Reliability of the simulation tool was established by using test retest and equivalence reliability tests in every measurement and the results were correlated using excel. The results showed a strong positive correlation with the average measure Correlation Coefficient of 0.97 at 95% confidence level and average p-value of .015.

The validation study showed that, with the use of relevant Weather files, it is possible to predict PIEC using Openstudio simulation tool in mid-rise office buildings especially in temperate-dry climate of Nigeria. This indicates that the simulation method can reliably reproduce real world conditions and it is therefore valid for the study.

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